

Social Connection in America™: Survey, Sources, and Copyright Information

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Barnes Family Foundation; 2025. doi:10.5281/zenodo.17410026

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Section A—Social Connection in America Survey (2025)

Lead-in Text:

This survey is about social connection and should take about 3-5 minutes.

Item #1:

How many close relationships do you have, people that you feel at ease with, can talk to about private matters?

1. 0
2. 1-2
3. 3-5
4. 6-9
5. 10 or more

Item #2:

Not counting your close friends or relatives, approximately how many other friends do you have? Include acquaintances as well as online friends. Would you say:

1. No other friends
2. 1 other friend
3. 2-5 other friends
4. 6-9 other friends
5. 10-14 other friends
6. 15-19 other friends
7. 20-49 other friends
8. 50-79 other friends
9. 80 or more other friends

Item #3:

In your day-to-day life, how often do you find yourself interacting with people who have different viewpoints or backgrounds than you?

1. Never
2. Rarely
3. Sometimes
4. Often
5. All the time

Item #4:

How often do you get the social and emotional support you need?

1. Always
2. Usually
3. Sometimes
4. Rarely
5. Never

Item #5:

Do you have someone you could turn to if you needed practical help, like getting a ride, doing chores, or other favors?

1. Always
2. Usually
3. Sometimes
4. Rarely
5. Never

Item #6:

I am content with my friendships and relationships.

- 0 – Strongly Disagree
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 – Strongly Agree

Item #7:

Overall, how satisfied are you with your personal relationships with family, friends, neighbors, and other people you know?

- 0 – Not at all satisfied
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 – Completely satisfied

Item #8:

How often do you feel lonely?

1. Always
2. Usually
3. Sometimes
4. Rarely
5. Never

Item #9:

How often do you experience stress with regard to your family or social relationships?

1. Never
2. Almost never (a few times a year or less)
3. Rarely (once a month or less)
4. Sometimes (a few times a month)
5. Often (once a week)
6. Very often (a few times a week)
7. Always (every day)

Item #10:

Not including people you live with, how often do you typically get together with people that you care about and feel close to?

1. Less than once a year or never
2. Once or twice a year
3. Every few months
4. Once or twice a month
5. Once or twice a week
6. Three or more times a week

Item #11:

In a typical week, and not including people you live with, how many times do you talk on the telephone or by video with the people that you care about and feel close to?

1. Never or less than once a week
2. 1 to 2 times a week
3. 3 to 4 times a week
4. 5 or more times

Item #12:

During the past 12 months, how many times did you attend religious services? (Do not include special occasions such as weddings, funerals, or other special events)

1. 0
2. 1 to 3
3. 4 to 11
4. 12 or more

Item #13:

During the past 12 months, how many times did you attend meetings of clubs or organizations you belong to? (Examples include community groups, unions, athletic groups, or school groups)

1. Do not belong to clubs or organizations
2. 0
3. 1 to 3
4. 4 to 11
5. 12 or more

Item #14:

In the past 12 months, how often did you volunteer for any organization or association? This includes activities you do infrequently or for children's schools or youth organizations.

1. Never
2. Less than once a month
3. Once a month
4. A few times a month
5. A few times a week
6. Basically every day

Item #15:

I feel like I belong in my local community.

1. Strongly disagree
2. Disagree
3. Slightly disagree
4. Slightly agree
5. Agree
6. Strongly agree

Item #16:

In the past 12 months, did you get together with other people from your neighborhood to do something positive for your neighborhood or the community?

1. Never
2. Less than once a month
3. Once a month
4. A few times a month
5. A few times a week
6. Basically every day

Item #17:

People in this neighborhood can be trusted.

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Don't know

Item #18:

People around here are willing to help their neighbors.

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Don't know

Item #19:

This is a close-knit neighborhood.

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Don't know

Item #20:

People in this neighborhood generally don't get along with each other.

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Don't know

Item #21:

People in this neighborhood do not share the same values.

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neither agree nor disagree
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree
6. Don't know

Item #22:

Overall, how satisfied are you with life as a whole these days?

- 0 – Not at all satisfied
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 – Completely satisfied

Item #23:

I have a sense of direction and purpose in life.

1. Strongly agree
2. Somewhat agree
3. Slightly agree
4. Don't know
5. Slightly disagree
6. Somewhat disagree
7. Strongly disagree

Item #24:

Would you say that in general your health is:

1. Excellent
2. Very Good
3. Good
4. Fair
5. Poor

Item #25:

In general, would you say that your mental health is:

1. Excellent
2. Very Good
3. Good
4. Fair
5. Poor

Item #26:

Has a doctor, nurse, or other health professional ever told you that you had a depressive disorder (including depression, major depression, dysthymia, or minor depression)?

1. Yes
2. No

Section B—Item Domains, Sourcing, and Copyright Information

Social Connection (Individual)

Structure

Items #1-3 - Social Networks (Individuals)

Item #1:

Source

- Newall, N. E. G., & Menec, V. H. (2020). A comparison of different definitions of social isolation using Canadian Longitudinal Study on Aging (CLSA) data. *Ageing and Society*, 40(12), 2671–2694. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0144686X19000801>

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Item #2:

Source

- Statistics Canada. (2025). *Survey on social connections - well-being in Canada, 2025*.
<https://www23.statcan.gc.ca/imdb/p2SV.pl?Function=getSurvey&Id=1566996#a2>

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Item #3:

Source

- Small, C., Yudkin, D., & Wylie, J. (2025). *The Connection Opportunity*. More in Common.
https://moreincommonus.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/The-Connection-Opportunity_More-in-Common_2025.pdf

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Items #10-13 - Social Isolation

Source

- National Center for Health Statistics. (2025). National Health Interview Survey (NHIS) Questionnaire. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
https://ftp.cdc.gov/pub/Health_Statistics/NCHS/Survey_Questionnaires/NHIS/2025/NHIS-English-Questionnaire.pdf

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Function

Items #4 & 5 - Social Support

Item #4:

Source

- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. (2012). Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System: 2010 survey data and documentation. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services.
https://www.cdc.gov/brfss/annual_data/annual_2010.htm

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Item #5:

Source

- Cubbin, C. (2015). Survey methodology of the geographic research on wellbeing (GROW) study. BMC Research Notes, 8, 402.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-015-1379-2>

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<https://bmresnotes.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13104-015-1379-2#appendices>

Changes to item or response set compared to source version

- The original item in the GROW study (Table 3) reported % who said “yes” to a question asking whether the participant has “Someone to help with practical help, like getting a ride, help with shopping/cooking a meal, or watching her children for a short time.”

Item #8 - Loneliness

Source

- National Center for Health Statistics. (2025). National Health Interview Survey (NHIS) Questionnaire. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
https://ftp.cdc.gov/pub/Health_Statistics/NCHS/Survey_Questionnaires/NHIS/2025/NHIS-English-Questionnaire.pdf

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- Copyright free for researchers without special permission.

Quality

Items #6 & 7 - Relationship Satisfaction

Item #6:

Source

- Campaign to End Loneliness. (2019). Measuring your impact on loneliness in later life.
<https://www.campaigntoendloneliness.org/wp-content/uploads/Loneliness-Measurement-Guidance1-1.pdf>
- VanderWeele, T.J. (2017). On the promotion of human flourishing. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, U.S.A., 31:8148-8156.
<https://www.pnas.org/content/pnas/114/31/8148.full.pdf>

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Item #7:

Source

- Eurostat. (2022). Methodological Guidelines and Description of EU-SILC Target Variables (Doc 65). European Commission.
<https://circabc.europa.eu/sd/a/8db0fafd-a762-4427-bd03-ec0ad72e2914/Methodological%20guidelines%202022%20operation%20v7.pdf>

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- See [Eurostat website](#).

Item #9 – Relationship Stress

Source

- Chari, R., Chang, C.-C., Sauter, S., Petrun Sayers, E., Huang, W., & Fisher, G. (2024). *NIOSH Worker Well-Being Questionnaire (WellBQ)*. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health.
<https://doi.org/10.26616/NIOSH PUB2021110revised052024>

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Community Connection

Item #14 – Formal Volunteering

Source

- U.S. Census Bureau. (2023). Current Population Survey, September 2023: Civic Engagement and Volunteering Technical Documentation.
<https://www2.census.gov/programs-surveys/cps/techdocs/cpssep23.pdf>

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Item #15 - Local Belonging

Source

- Walton, G. M., & Cohen, G. L. (2007). A question of belonging: race, social fit, and achievement. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 92(1), 82–96.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.92.1.82>

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- Copyrighted (Walton & Cohen, 2007). This item is adapted from a published social-belonging scale in academic research. The original scale (see [Walton & Cohen's belonging measures on sparqtools.org](#)) is copyrighted by the authors/journal, but it is freely used in research with proper citation (no license fee required).

Item #16 - Informal Participation

Source

- U.S. Census Bureau. (2023). Current Population Survey, September 2023: Civic Engagement and Volunteering Technical Documentation.
<https://www2.census.gov/programs-surveys/cps/techdocs/cpssep23.pdf>

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data products are in the public domain and may be freely used, reproduced, or distributed by anyone within the U.S.

Items #17-21 - PHDCN Social Cohesion module

Source

- Earls, F., Brooks-Gunn, J., Raudenbush, S., & Sampson, R. (1994). Project on Human Development in Chicago Neighborhoods: Community Survey, 1994-1995. Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research [distributor]. <https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/NACJD/studies/2766/versions/V4/variables>

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-

Well-Being

Item #22 - Subjective Well-Being (life satisfaction)

Source

- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2013). *OECD guidelines on measuring subjective well-being*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264191655-en>

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Item #23 - Direction & Purpose in Life

Source

- Ryff, C. D. (1989). Happiness is everything, or is it? Explorations on the meaning of psychological well-being. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 57(6), 1069-1081. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.57.6.1069>
- Full scales: [Psychological Wellbeing Scale | SPARQtools](#)

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- Copyright from Dr. Carol Ryff: cryff@wisc.edu

Item #24 – Self Rated Physical Health

Source

- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). (2023). Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System Survey Questionnaire. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
<https://www.cdc.gov/brfss/questionnaires/index.htm>

License/Copyright Information

- Public domain.

Items #25 & 26 – Self Rated Mental Health

Item #25:

Source

- Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality. (2024). MEPS HC-243: 2022 Full Year Consolidated Data File. Medical Expenditure Panel Survey.
https://meps.ahrq.gov/mepsweb/data_stats/download_data_files_detail.jsp?cboPufNumber=HC-243

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Item #26:

Source

- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). (2023). Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System Survey Questionnaire. U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention.
<https://www.cdc.gov/brfss/questionnaires/index.htm>

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